

Public Relations Strategies of the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) in Enhancing Road Safety Awareness and Behaviour among Commercial Motorists in Adamawa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Road traffic accidents remain a major public health challenge in Nigeria, necessitating effective communication interventions for behavioural change. This study examined the effectiveness of Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) public relations (PR) strategies in promoting road safety among commercial motorists in Adamawa State, Nigeria. Specifically, it assessed PR strategies employed by FRSC, levels of awareness created, motorists' attitudes, behavioural compliance, and the relationship between PR exposure, attitude, and behaviour. A descriptive survey design was adopted, involving 321 respondents selected through multi-stage sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analysed using descriptive statistics and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Findings revealed that FRSC utilises a mix of PR strategies dominated by mass media campaigns, enforcement-based communication, and institutional engagements, while digital and participatory approaches were less utilised. Although awareness of road safety messages was high among motorists (grand mean = 3.96), attitudes toward FRSC PR strategies were generally negative (grand mean = 2.14), and behavioural compliance remained low (grand mean = 1.96). Correlation analysis indicated no significant relationship between PR exposure and attitude ($r = 0.062$, $p > 0.05$), PR exposure and behaviour ($r = 0.048$, $p > 0.05$), and attitude and behaviour ($r = 0.089$, $p > 0.05$), suggesting a disconnect between message exposure and behavioural outcomes. The study concludes that FRSC PR strategies generate awareness but do not significantly influence attitudes or compliance among commercial motorists. It recommends the integration of participatory, trust-based, and behaviourally oriented communication approaches alongside enforcement mechanisms to enhance road safety outcomes.

Keywords: Public relations, road safety, FRSC, commercial motorists, behavioural compliance, Nigeria.

Introduction

Road traffic accidents remain one of the most devastating yet preventable public health crises globally. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2020), approximately 1.19 million people die annually from road traffic crashes, while millions more suffer injuries, disabilities, and long-term socio-economic consequences. The burden of these fatalities falls disproportionately on low- and middle-income countries, which account for about 90% of global road traffic deaths despite having fewer vehicles than developed nations (WHO, 2020). Beyond the loss of lives, road crashes impose enormous economic costs through reduced productivity, loss of human capital, increased healthcare expenditures, and diminished economic growth (Adekunle, 2010; Dalal & Yousefi, 2021; Gu, et al. 2025). Nigeria remains one of the countries most affected by this challenge. The WHO (2013) ranked Nigeria among the countries with the highest road traffic fatality rates globally. Recent statistics indicate that thousands of deaths continue to occur annually

despite sustained interventions by the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) and other stakeholders (FRSC, 2023; Allwell; 2026). Evidence further suggests that a significant proportion of these crashes result from human factors such as speeding, reckless overtaking, distracted driving, overloading, and driving under the influence of substances (Okonkwo, 2024; Inah, 2025). Since these behaviours are largely preventable, communication-based interventions are critical for improving road safety outcomes.

Communication has long been established as a critical instrument for shaping public awareness, attitudes, and behavioural outcomes in health and safety campaigns (Bandura, 1986; Hovland et al., 1953; McGuire, 1989; Rice & Atkin, 2013; Rogers, 2003; Kreps, 2014). Current empirical evidence indicates that well-designed communication interventions significantly influence individual perceptions, enhance compliance with safety regulations, and promote desirable behavioural change (Esse, 2021; Abdul-Wahab, 2016; Nnabuife et al., 2023; Ucheobi et al., 2023; Shadrach, 2024). Collectively, these studies demonstrate that communication is not merely informational but also behavioural in its impact, particularly in domains where public safety compliance is essential.

Within the broader spectrum of communication strategies, public relations occupies a distinctive position due to its emphasis on strategic relationship-building, stakeholder engagement, persuasion, trust development, and behaviour modification (Chiakaan & Chile, 2020). This functional role is theoretically reinforced by Jefkins' (1988) Public Relations Transfer Process Model, which conceptualises PR as a mechanism for transforming ignorance, apathy, and negative attitudes into knowledge, interest, acceptance, and ultimately behavioural compliance. In this sense, PR operates as a structured behavioural change process rather than a purely communicative activity (Chiakaan & Chile, 2020).

Literature increasingly recognises public relations as an effective mechanism for influencing behaviour across multiple applied domains. In marketing communication, studies have shown that PR enhances brand engagement, consumer trust, and purchase-related behaviour (Chidiadi, 2020; Ekakitie-Emonena & Sado, 2023). In health promotion, empirical findings similarly demonstrate its effectiveness in improving health awareness, service uptake, and preventive behaviours (Elrod & Fortenberry, 2020; Ivwighren, Ochonogor & Joloko, 2024). Furthermore, in environmental sustainability, PR has been shown to facilitate environmental awareness, stakeholder engagement, and organisational legitimacy in sustainability communication (Tworzydło et al., 2024). In the context of public policy implementation, evidence suggests that PR contributes to policy visibility, public trust, and compliance, thereby enhancing implementation effectiveness (Kondolele et al., 2025; Rutere & Simiyu, 2024).

Despite this growing body of evidence, the application of public relations within the road safety domain remains relatively underexplored. Only a limited number of studies (e.g., Devlin, 2023b; Esteban, 2020) have explicitly examined PR in the context of road safety communication, and these investigations are largely situated in developed countries such as Australia and Spain. While these studies provide valuable insights, their findings have limited contextual transferability to developing regions, particularly sub-Saharan Africa and Nigeria, where road safety challenges are shaped by distinct infrastructural constraints, enforcement weaknesses, and socio-cultural behavioural patterns. Therefore, there remains a significant gap in context-specific research that examines how PR strategies can be adapted to address road safety challenges in Nigeria. This gap is particularly critical given the country's high rate of road traffic fatalities and the need for communication strategies that integrate systemic infrastructural issues, stakeholder dynamics, and

evidence-based behavioural interventions. Addressing this deficiency is essential for advancing both theoretical understanding and practical application of public relations in road safety management within Nigerian and the Global South context. Against this backdrop this study examined the application of PR by the Federal Road Safety Corps' (FRSC) in promoting road safety among commercial motorists in Adamawa State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to achieve the following:

1. To identify the Public Relations strategies employed by the FRSC in disseminating road safety messages to commercial motorists in Adamawa State.
2. To determine the level of awareness created through FRSC Public Relations strategies on road safety measures among commercial motorists in Adamawa State.
3. To assess the attitudes of commercial motorists toward FRSC Public Relations strategies for road safety promotion in Adamawa State.
4. To examine the behavioural compliance of commercial motorists influenced by FRSC Public Relations strategies on road safety measures in Adamawa State.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey design. The design is appropriate because it enables the collection of quantifiable data from a large population to examine the relationship between public relations communication and road safety awareness among commercial motorists.

Population and Research Setting

The population comprised commercial motorists registered with NURTW (3,889) in Adamawa State. The population is suitable because it captures both message receivers (drivers) and institutional communicators (FRSC).

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A sample size of 357 respondents was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table, which is appropriate for ensuring statistical representativeness at a 95% confidence level. A multi-stage sampling technique (stratification, purposive selection of locations, and simple random sampling) was used to ensure proportional and unbiased selection of respondents across senatorial zones and motor parks.

Instrumentation and Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, suitable for obtaining standardized and measurable responses. Validity was ensured through expert review, while reliability was confirmed using a pilot test and Cronbach's alpha (≥ 0.70) to ensure internal consistency. The questionnaire was appropriate because it allows objective measurement of awareness and behavioural outcomes related to PR communication exposure.

Method of Data Analysis

Data were analysed using descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) to summarise respondents' views in a clear, quantitative form that facilitates objective interpretation of patterns in awareness, attitudes, and behavioural compliance. In addition, inferential analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was employed to examine the relationship between exposure to FRSC Public Relations strategies (independent variable) and motorists' attitudes and

behavioural compliance (dependent variables), thereby enabling the testing of hypothesised associations between communication exposure and road safety outcomes.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Demographic Information of respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	233	72.6
Female	88	27.4
Age		
20-30	91	28.3
31-40	77	24.0
41-50	65	20.2
51-60	51	15.9
61 and above	37	11.5
Educational Qualification		
Senior Secondary Certificate	134	41.7
National Diploma/NCE	103	32.1
Bachelor’s Degree/HND	67	20.9
Master’s Degree	5	1.6
Ph.D./Doctorate	0	0.0
Others	22	6.9
Occupation		
Civil Servant	67	20.9
Self-employed/Business	100	32.2
Commercial Driver	84	26.2
Transport Union Official	45	14.0
Others	25	7.8

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The demographic profile of respondents shows that the sample was predominantly male, largely young to middle-aged, moderately educated, and occupationally concentrated in transport-related and informal economic activities. Specifically, males formed the majority, reflecting the gendered nature of commercial driving, while most respondents fell within the economically active age brackets, indicating a population actively engaged in road usage. Educational attainment was generally sufficient for interpreting communication materials, with most respondents having at least secondary education or post-secondary qualifications. Occupationally, respondents were mainly self-employed individuals and commercial drivers, reinforcing the relevance of the sample to road safety and transport communication research, as it captures the perspectives of those directly exposed to FRSC public relations and road safety campaigns.

Table 2. Public Relations Strategies used by FRSC in Promoting Road Safety measures among Commercial Motorists (n = 321)

PR Strategy	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Decision
Radio/TV campaigns	145 (45.2%)	100 (31.2%)	40 (12.5%)	25 (7.8%)	11 (3.4%)	4.08	Agreed
Social media messages	8 (2.5%)	12 (3.7%)	30 (9.3%)	85 (26.5%)	186 (58.0%)	1.24	Disagreed
Driver enlightenment workshops	5 (1.6%)	10 (3.1%)	20 (6.2%)	90 (28.0%)	196 (61.1%)	1.07	Disagreed
Flyers/posters	70 (21.8%)	95 (29.6%)	70 (21.8%)	50 (15.6%)	36 (11.2%)	3.15	Agreed
Roadside sensitisation	110 (34.3%)	100 (31.2%)	55 (17.1%)	35 (10.9%)	21 (6.5%)	3.69	Agreed
Road shows/rallies	40 (12.5%)	60 (18.7%)	80 (24.9%)	75 (23.4%)	66 (20.6%)	2.28	Disagreed
Transport union engagement	95 (29.6%)	92 (28.7%)	60 (18.7%)	40 (12.5%)	34 (10.6%)	3.34	Agreed
FRSC checkpoints/public warnings	150 (46.7%)	95 (29.6%)	40 (12.5%)	22 (6.9%)	14 (4.4%)	4.05	Agreed
Religious institutions	78 (24.3%)	92 (28.7%)	70 (21.8%)	45 (14.0%)	36 (11.2%)	3.27	Agreed
Traditional leaders engagement	25 (7.8%)	40 (12.5%)	80 (24.9%)	90 (28.0%)	86 (26.8%)	2.03	Disagreed
Grand Mean						3.11	Agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The results indicate that the FRSC employs a range of Public Relations strategies to promote road safety among commercial motorists in Adamawa State, although their levels of utilisation and effectiveness vary considerably. Mass media strategies and FRSC checkpoints/public warnings recorded the highest levels of agreement, reflecting their strong visibility and frequent use among motorists. Similarly, roadside sensitisation, transport union engagement, religious institutions, and flyers/posters were also rated positively, indicating moderate effectiveness of these conventional communication channels. In contrast, digital and participatory community-based strategies, including social media messages, driver enlightenment workshops, road shows/rallies, and engagement of traditional leaders, were rated below the acceptance threshold, suggesting limited reach or effectiveness among respondents. The grand mean of 3.11 suggests that FRSC Public Relations strategies are moderately effective in disseminating road safety messages, with greater reliance on traditional and enforcement-linked communication approaches.

Table 3. Level of Awareness Created through FRSC Public Relations Strategies on Road Safety Measures (n = 321)

Awareness Indicators (PR-driven)	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Decision
Awareness of speed limits through FRSC campaigns	150 (46.7%)	100 (31.2%)	40 (12.5%)	20 (6.2%)	11 (3.4%)	4.09	Agreed
Awareness of seatbelt use campaigns	140 (43.6%)	105 (32.7%)	45 (14.0%)	20 (6.2%)	11 (3.4%)	4.07	Agreed
Awareness of dangers of overloading	130 (40.5%)	110 (34.3%)	50 (15.6%)	20 (6.2%)	11 (3.4%)	4.03	Agreed
Awareness of drunk-driving campaigns	120 (37.4%)	110 (34.3%)	55 (17.1%)	25 (7.8%)	11 (3.4%)	3.95	Agreed
Awareness of FRSC penalties and sanctions	145 (45.2%)	95 (29.6%)	50 (15.6%)	20 (6.2%)	11 (3.4%)	4.08	Agreed
Awareness of road safety education programmes	100 (31.2%)	110 (34.3%)	60 (18.7%)	35 (10.9%)	16 (5.0%)	3.76	Agreed
Awareness of accident prevention messages	135 (42.1%)	100 (31.2%)	55 (17.1%)	20 (6.2%)	11 (3.4%)	4.03	Agreed
Awareness of emergency response procedures	90 (28.0%)	110 (34.3%)	70 (21.8%)	35 (10.9%)	16 (5.0%)	3.70	Agreed
Grand Mean						3.96	Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2025

he results indicate a generally high level of awareness among commercial motorists regarding road safety measures disseminated through FRSC Public Relations strategies in Adamawa State. Specifically, respondents demonstrated strong awareness of key safety messages, with speed limit regulations (Mean = 4.09), penalties and sanctions (Mean = 4.08), seatbelt use (Mean = 4.07), and accident prevention campaigns (Mean = 4.03) recording the highest mean scores, suggesting effective communication and message penetration in these areas. Awareness of overloading risks (Mean = 4.03) and drunk-driving campaigns (Mean = 3.95) was also high, indicating consistent exposure to critical behavioural safety messages. Although slightly lower, awareness of road safety education programmes (Mean = 3.76) and emergency response procedures (Mean = 3.70) still fell within the accepted threshold, reflecting moderate but adequate reach.

Table 4. Attitudes of Commercial Motorists Toward FRSC Public Relations Strategies for Road Safety Promotion (n = 321)

Attitude Statements	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Decision
FRSC PR campaigns are convincing and persuasive	35 (10.9%)	50 (15.6%)	60 (18.7%)	100 (31.2%)	76 (23.7%)	2.27	Negative
FRSC PR messages are credible and trustworthy	30 (9.3%)	45 (14.0%)	55 (17.1%)	110 (34.3%)	81 (25.2%)	2.14	Negative
I find FRSC PR strategies relevant to my driving practice	32 (10.0%)	48 (15.0%)	60 (18.7%)	95 (29.6%)	86 (26.8%)	2.21	Negative
FRSC communication channels are appropriate for motorists	25 (7.8%)	40 (12.5%)	65 (20.2%)	110 (34.3%)	81 (25.2%)	2.12	Negative
FRSC PR campaigns motivate compliance with road safety rules	28 (8.7%)	42 (13.1%)	60 (18.7%)	105 (32.7%)	86 (26.8%)	2.10	Negative
I am satisfied with FRSC road safety communication efforts	20 (6.2%)	35 (10.9%)	55 (17.1%)	120 (37.4%)	91 (28.3%)	1.96	Negative
FRSC PR strategies positively influence my driving attitude	30 (9.3%)	45 (14.0%)	65 (20.2%)	100 (31.2%)	81 (25.2%)	2.18	Negative
Grand Mean						2.14	Negative

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The results indicate that commercial motorists in Adamawa State generally hold a negative attitude toward FRSC Public Relations strategies for road safety promotion. Across all measured indicators, mean scores fall below the acceptance threshold of 3.00, reflecting widespread dissatisfaction and low perceived effectiveness of FRSC communication efforts. Specifically, respondents rated FRSC PR campaigns as weak in persuasiveness (Mean = 2.27), credibility (Mean = 2.14), relevance to driving practice (Mean = 2.21), and appropriateness of communication channels (Mean = 2.12). Similarly, the ability of FRSC messages to motivate compliance (Mean = 2.10) and positively influence driving behaviour (Mean = 2.18) was rated low, while overall satisfaction with FRSC communication efforts recorded the lowest mean score (Mean = 1.96). The grand mean of 2.14 further confirms a generally unfavourable attitude toward FRSC PR strategies and messages among commercial motorists.

Table: Behavioural Compliance of Commercial Motorists Influenced by FRSC Public Relations Strategies on Road Safety Measures (n = 321)

Behavioural Indicators	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Decision
I consistently use seatbelts while driving	20 (6.2%)	35 (10.9%)	50 (15.6%)	110 (34.3%)	106 (33.0%)	1.92	Low compliance
I obey FRSC speed limits regulations	18 (5.6%)	30 (9.3%)	55 (17.1%)	115 (35.8%)	103 (32.1%)	1.87	Low compliance
I avoid overloading passengers or goods	22 (6.9%)	32 (10.0%)	60 (18.7%)	110 (34.3%)	97 (30.2%)	1.96	Low compliance
I comply with traffic signs and road markings	25 (7.8%)	40 (12.5%)	65 (20.2%)	105 (32.7%)	86 (26.8%)	2.11	Low compliance
I avoid driving under fatigue or stress conditions	15 (4.7%)	28 (8.7%)	60 (18.7%)	120 (37.4%)	98 (30.5%)	1.82	Low compliance
I avoid use of phone while driving	18 (5.6%)	25 (7.8%)	55 (17.1%)	120 (37.4%)	103 (32.1%)	1.80	Low compliance
I respond appropriately to FRSC road safety messages	30 (9.3%)	45 (14.0%)	60 (18.7%)	100 (31.2%)	86 (26.8%)	2.18	Low compliance
I regularly maintain my vehicle for road safety	25 (7.8%)	40 (12.5%)	70 (21.8%)	95 (29.6%)	91 (28.3%)	2.03	Low compliance
Grand Mean						1.96	Low compliance

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The findings indicate generally poor behavioural compliance among commercial motorists with road safety measures influenced by FRSC Public Relations strategies in Adamawa State. Across all indicators, mean scores fall below the acceptable threshold of 3.00, reflecting low adherence to key safety practices such as seatbelt use (Mean = 1.92), compliance with speed limits (Mean = 1.87), avoidance of overloading (Mean = 1.96), and adherence to traffic signs (Mean = 2.11). Similarly, critical risky behaviours such as driving under fatigue (Mean = 1.82) and phone use while driving (Mean = 1.80) remain prevalent, indicating weak behavioural change despite ongoing FRSC communication efforts. While relatively higher but still inadequate scores were observed for responsiveness to FRSC messages (Mean = 2.18) and vehicle maintenance practices (Mean = 2.03), these do not translate into acceptable compliance levels. The grand mean of 1.96 further confirms overall low behavioural compliance, suggesting that FRSC Public Relations

strategies have limited effectiveness in converting awareness and attitudes into safe driving practices among commercial motorists.

Table: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) between PR Exposure, Attitude, and Behavioural Compliance (n = 321)

Compliance (n = 321)

Variables	PR Exposure	Attitude	Behavioural Compliance
PR Exposure	1.000	0.062	0.048
Attitude	0.062	1.000	0.089
Behavioural Compliance	0.048	0.089	1.000

Note: Correlation is not significant at $p > 0.05$ (2-tailed)

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis reveals that there is no statistically significant relationship between exposure to FRSC Public Relations strategies, attitudes of commercial motorists, and their behavioural compliance with road safety measures in Adamawa State. Specifically, the relationship between PR exposure and attitude ($r = 0.062, p > 0.05$) is positive but extremely weak and not statistically significant, indicating that increased exposure to FRSC communication strategies does not meaningfully translate into favourable attitudes toward road safety messages. Similarly, the relationship between PR exposure and behavioural compliance ($r = 0.048, p > 0.05$) is negligible and not significant, suggesting that PR messages have minimal influence on actual driving behaviour. Furthermore, the association between attitude and behavioural compliance ($r = 0.089, p > 0.05$) is also weak and statistically insignificant, implying that even favourable attitudes do not necessarily result in improved compliance with road safety regulations. The results suggest a disconnect between FRSC Public Relations strategies and behavioural outcomes, indicating that existing communication efforts may not be sufficiently persuasive or impactful to produce measurable behavioural change among commercial motorists.

Discussion of Findings

The study sought to identify the PR Strategies Used by FRSC in promoting road safety. The outcome indicates that the FRSC employs a mix of Public Relations strategies in promoting road safety, with mass media campaigns, enforcement-linked communication (checkpoints/public warnings), roadside sensitisation, and institutional engagement (transport unions and religious bodies) being the most dominant, while digital platforms, driver enlightenment workshops, road shows/rallies, and traditional leader engagement were relatively weak. This suggests a preference for top-down, mass-oriented and enforcement-supported communication approaches rather than participatory or digitally driven PR strategies. The implication is that FRSC communication remains largely institutional and compliance-driven, which aligns with the assumptions of the Public Relations Transfer Process Model (Jefkins, 1988) that emphasizes structured message transmission from organization to publics to shift behaviour. This supports findings by Esteban et al. (2020) and Macauley (2021), who noted that mass media and formal institutional communication remain dominant in road safety campaigns, but contrasts with Ucheobi et al. (2023), who found stronger effectiveness for interpersonal and multi-channel engagement. The relatively weak role of social media and community-driven PR in this study is unexpected given

the global shift toward digital communication, suggesting a digital divide and contextual infrastructural limitations in Nigeria's transport communication ecosystem.

The study also examined the level of awareness of the motorist regarding road safety. Findings suggest a generally high level of awareness among commercial motorists regarding FRSC road safety messages, particularly on speed limits, seatbelt use, penalties, and accident prevention. This indicates that FRSC Public Relations strategies are effective at the cognitive stage of communication impact, where publics acquire knowledge and awareness. The implication is that FRSC communication successfully achieves the knowledge and interest stages of Jefkins' Transfer Process Model, where ignorance is reduced and awareness is generated. This finding aligns strongly with Nnabuife et al. (2023) and Ucheobi et al. (2023), who similarly reported high awareness levels among drivers exposed to FRSC campaigns. It also supports Two-Step Flow Theory, as awareness may be reinforced through opinion leaders such as transport unions and peers within motor parks. However, despite this expected outcome, the finding reveals a critical gap: high awareness does not automatically translate into behavioural compliance, which suggests a breakdown in the communication-to-action continuum, a limitation also noted in Esse (2021) who argued that awareness campaigns alone are insufficient for behavioural transformation.

Furthermore, the study examined the attitude of the motorists toward FRSC road safety PR messages. Findings suggest that the motorists generally hold a negative attitude toward FRSC Public Relations strategies, reflecting low perceived credibility, relevance, persuasiveness, and motivational value of the campaigns. This indicates that while awareness is high, affective acceptance of FRSC messages is weak, meaning the communication process is failing at the attitude formation stage. The implication is that FRSC messages may be cognitively received but are not emotionally or socially internalized, which limits their behavioural influence. Theoretically, this partially contradicts the Jefkins Transfer Model, which assumes a relatively linear progression from awareness to acceptance; instead, the findings suggest a blocked transition between awareness and acceptance stages. Empirically, this supports Shadrach (2024), who also found poor attitudes among drivers despite exposure to FRSC messages, and Nwadinigwe et al. (2019), who noted that compliance is influenced by deeper behavioural and experiential factors beyond communication exposure. The unexpected aspect here is that despite high awareness, attitudes remain negative, suggesting that FRSC communication may lack credibility, cultural resonance, or participatory framing, thereby weakening trust and acceptance.

In addition, the study revealed low behavioural compliance among commercial motorists with road safety regulations, including seatbelt use, speed control, avoidance of overloading, and phone use while driving. This indicates that FRSC Public Relations strategies have limited effectiveness in producing actual behavioural change. The implication is that communication efforts are largely failing at the final stage of the behavioural transformation process, where knowledge and attitudes should translate into action. This finding directly challenges the assumptions of the Jefkins Transfer Process Model, which presumes that effective communication leads to behavioural acceptance, suggesting that external variables such as enforcement weakness, economic pressures, and cultural driving norms interfere with message adoption. This aligns with Esteban et al. (2020) and Esse (2021), who emphasized that communication alone is insufficient without structural enforcement and sustained behavioural reinforcement. The finding is particularly significant because it shows a disconnect between awareness and practice, reinforcing the argument that road safety behaviour is shaped more by contextual and systemic factors than communication alone.

The correlation analysis revealed no significant relationship between exposure to FRSC Public Relations strategies and both attitude and behavioural compliance, indicating a weak or absent linear relationship among the study variables. This implies that exposure alone does not predict attitudinal or behavioural change among commercial motorists. This aligns with Macauley (2021) and Shadrach (2024), who reported that exposure does not necessarily guarantee behavioural change. The unexpected outcome here is the complete lack of statistical relationship, which suggests that FRSC PR strategies may function more as informational campaigns rather than behavioural change interventions, highlighting a major effectiveness gap in road safety communication.

Conclusion

This study examined the effectiveness of Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) Public Relations strategies in promoting road safety among commercial motorists in Adamawa State. It reported that FRSC employs a heterogeneous mix of public relations strategies, with greater reliance on mass media, enforcement-linked communication, and institutional engagement. It further established a high level of awareness of road safety messages among commercial motorists, yet this cognitive outcome does not translate into favourable attitudes or behavioural compliance. This suggests a disconnect between message exposure and behavioural adoption, reinforcing the need for more participatory, trust-building, and context-sensitive communication approaches. The results also imply that road safety communication alone, without strong reinforcement mechanisms and behavioural nudging structures, is unlikely to yield sustained compliance among commercial motorists. For policy and practice, FRSC communication strategy may require reorientation toward integrated behaviour change communication models that combine public relations, enforcement consistency, and community-level engagement.

Despite the contribution of the study, it is limited by its reliance on self-reported data, which may be subject to response bias and social desirability effects and geographically confined to Adamawa State, which limits the generalisability of the findings to other regions with different socio-cultural and transport dynamics. Future research should adopt experimental designs to better establish causal relationships between FRSC communication strategies and behavioural change outcomes. Comparative studies across multiple geopolitical zones in Nigeria are recommended to enhance generalisability and identify regional variations in road safety communication effectiveness.

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